

Supplementary Materials

Figure S1. Velocity components differences (columns) for three different contrasts (rows) at 1-km resolution. Top row: ClimateNA (Wang et al. 2016) vs. ERA5 (Hersbach et al. 2020); Middle row: ClimateNA vs. CRCM5; Bottom row: ERA5 vs. CRCM5. First column: \log_{10} (spatial gradient, mm km^{-1}) for 1981-2010 baseline period; Second column: temporal gradient (mm yr^{-1}) from baseline (1981-2010) to end-of- century (2071-2100) based on CanESM2 (RCP 8.5); Third column: \log_{10} (velocity +1), where velocity (km yr^{-1}) = temporal gradient / spatial gradient.

Figure S2. Velocity components (columns) for three different climate products (rows) at 22-km resolution. Top row: ClimateNA resampled from native 1-km grid (Wang et al. 2016); Middle row: ERA5 resampled from native 0.25° grid (Hersbach et al. 2020); Bottom row: CRCM5 resampled from native ~0.22° grid. First column: $\log_{10}(\text{spatial gradient, mm km}^{-1})$ for 1981-2010 baseline period; Second column: temporal gradient (mm yr^{-1}) from baseline (1981-2010) to end-of-century (2071-2100) based on CanESM2; Third column: $\log_{10}(\text{velocity} + 1)$, where velocity (km yr^{-1}) = temporal gradient / spatial gradient.

Figure S3. PET velocity [$\log_{10}(\text{velocity} + 1)$, km yr^{-1}] across different climate products (rows) and GCMs (columns) at 1-km resolution. Top row: ClimateNA; Middle row: ERA5 lapse-rate downscaled from native 0.25° grid; Bottom row: CRCM5 lapse-rate-downscaled from native $\sim 0.22^\circ$ grid. First column: CanESM2; Second row: MPI-ESM-LR; Third row: CNRM-CM5.